

Demographic Questionnaire

[omitted for review]

November 2025

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Instructions

This questionnaire collects background information to describe the participant profile. All responses will remain confidential and will be used solely for research analysis.

Participant Information

1. Age: _____ Gender: _____
2. Highest educational level:
 Undergraduate Master's Doctorate Other: _____
3. Current role or occupation:

4. Primary area of expertise:
 Blockchain
 Software Quality
 Software Engineering
 Other: _____
5. Years of professional or research experience:

6. Experience with blockchain or software quality (in years):

7. Familiarity with quality evaluation tools or metrics frameworks:
 Beginner Intermediate Advanced